

Algorithmic Approach for Computation of Binomial Expansions

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Abstract: Nowadays, the growing complexity of mathematical and computational modelling demands the simplicity of mathematical and combinatorial equations for solving today's scientific problems and challenges. This paper presents the computation of binomial expansions in algorithmic way. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to compute the multiple summations of a geometric series [1-12], a new idea stimulated his mind to create a new type of geometric series. As a result, a combinatorial geometric series was developed with new idea of binomial coefficients. The computation of combinatorial geometric series and its properties are explained in the next section.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [13-21] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

3. Computation of Binomial Expansions

Let us compute the following binomial expansions step by step procedures.

Step 1: $V_0^2 + V_1^2 = 2V_0^1 + V_1^1$.

Step 2: $V_0^3 + V_1^3 + V_2^3 = 3V_0^2 + 2V_1^2 + V_2^2$.

Step 3: $V_0^4 + V_1^4 + V_2^4 + V_3^4 = 4V_0^3 + 3V_1^3 + 2V_2^3 + V_3^3$.

Similarly, we can continue to compute the above expressions up to **Step n** as follows:

$$\text{Step n: } \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^{r+1} = (r+1)V_0^r + rV_1^r + (r-1)V_2^r + \cdots + 3V_{(r-2)}^r + 2V_{(r-1)}^r + V_r^r.$$

4. Conclusion

In this article, algorithmic approach for computation of binomial expansions was introduced using the binomial coefficients defined in combinatorial geometric series. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real world problems.

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